

UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON
MSc in Cognitive and Decision Sciences

**Modelling Semantic Memory &
Its Impairments Following Neural Damage**

Candidate Number: CDS12

Supervisor: Rick Cooper

Date: September 2010

Contents

Summary	1
1 Introduction	2
1.1 Impairments of Semantic Memory	2
1.2 PDP Models of Semantic Memory	3
1.2.1 The Rogers et al. Model	3
1.2.2 The Gotts and Plaut Model	5
1.3 Aims of this Study	7
2 A Boltzmann Machine Model of Semantic Memory	8
2.1 The Boltzmann Machine	8
2.1.1 Interpretation of Network States	8
2.1.2 Simulated Annealing, Thermal Equilibrium & Learning	9
2.1.3 Motivation for Using a Boltzmann Machine	10
2.2 Implementation Specific Details	10
2.3 Patterns	11
2.3.1 Verbal Input	12
2.3.2 Visual Input	12
2.3.3 Name Input	12
2.3.4 Pattern Similarity Structure	13
2.4 Training in the Model	16
2.5 Internal Representations	17
3 Evaluating the Model	20
3.1 Modelling Damage	20
3.2 Confrontation Naming	21
3.2.1 Modelling Method	21
3.2.2 Overall Naming Results	21
3.2.3 Naming Results in Different Domains	22
3.3 Word-to-Picture Matching	23
3.3.1 Modelling Method	23
3.3.2 Longitudinal and Cross-sectional Results	24
4 Discussion	26
4.1 Modelling Neural Damage	26
4.1.1 Semantic Dementia	26
4.1.2 Herpes Simplex Virus Encephalitis	27
4.2 Proposed Improvements and Extensions	28
4.3 Conclusion	29

References	30
A Training Schedule	32
A.1 High-level Training	32
A.2 Plus Phase	32
A.3 Minus Phases	32
A.4 Updating Unit States	33
A.5 Annealing	33
A.6 Collecting Co-occurrence Statistics	34
A.7 Adjusting Weights	34
B Neuromodulatory System	35
B.1 Synaptic Depression	35
B.2 Neuromodulation	36
B.3 Effect on Model	37
B.4 Disrupting the Neuromodulatory System	37

Summary

This project consists of a computational model of semantic memory; the underlying architecture of which, is a Boltzmann machine, a kind of attractor neural network. The general specification for the model and the set of training patterns are derived from Rogers et al. (2004). The framework contains a semantic store, which has access to streams of high-level perceptual and linguistic input features and equivalent forms of output. The semantic layer is equipped with the ability to internalise the structure found in the input, thus creating amodal semantic concepts.

To evaluate the sophistication of the model a comparison is made with semantically impaired patients. For this reason, damage is imposed, in a range of severity values, paralleling temporal lobe lesions. The overall extent, and category- or modality- specificity, of this degradation is determined using a battery of semantic tests, as given to patients with semantic impairments.

Results from these tests are shown to follow a qualitatively analogous trend to the scores achieved by semantic patients. The damaged model provides an attractor-based explanation for the patient data. Nonetheless, it is believed that this model, has too narrow a scope rendering it unable to capture all the details of semantic dementia, and therefore, the semantic system in general. Thus, some extensions are proposed: a neuromodulatory system (Gotts & Plaut, 2002); and a trainable executive, decision making, semantic module (Lambon Ralph et al., 2007).

1 Introduction

The cognitive processes that derive, categorise and form relations over factual knowledge, have concerned philosophy and science for hundreds of years. Semantic memory is usually described as consisting of context-free knowledge, or the ability of “knowing” something (Tulving, 1987). Despite the complexities regarding the emergence of meaning, such concepts appear, intuitively, to be an abstraction over a set of experiences collected gradually over time. In order to understand the semantic system, the neurological infrastructure must be located and understood. The temporal lobes, especially the left, have been shown, in neuroimaging studies, to be extensively activated during semantic tasks (Tyler et al., 2003).

1.1 Impairments of Semantic Memory

Warrington (1975) first described patients with a dissociable semantic deficit. These patients lacked the ability to specifically name and provide details for familiar objects, although they were able to identify the general category to which stimuli belong. This disorder is known as semantic dementia (SD), the fluent form of frontotemporal dementia, and is caused by bilateral atrophy of the anterior temporal lobes. Temporal lobe progressive neurodegeneration is the underlying cause of SD, which culminates in a cognitive deficit of fundamental language and memory skills, and severe object agnosia; a deficit purely of semantic memory (Hodges et al., 1992). SD provides a functionally and anatomically distinct impairment of semantic memory, aiding in modelling and in locating the regions responsible for semantic processing.

SD patients show a sensitivity to word frequency, but not semantic relatedness nor the speed of presentation; their semantic abilities are consistently poor. SD patients often make the following errors: *a*) they provide a super-category, where healthy individuals would give a more specific name, e.g., “animal” instead of “dog”; *b*) they also extend familiar/typical labels to semantically related objects, e.g., “cat” instead of “dog”; *c*) they remember general or common properties more robustly than rarer features, so they are strongly affected by the familiarity frequency of words in their environment; and *d*) they also show impairment in “pre-semantic” (Jefferies et al., 2010) tasks such as reading aloud, past tense generation, spelling to dictation, lexical decision, object decision, colour decision and delayed picture copying .

In contrast, another form of deficit, that of selective loss of knowledge in specific categories, is found in a different set of patients with damage to similar cortical areas. One of the aetiologies is the herpes simplex encephalitis virus (HSVE), which decreases the concentration of grey matter in the anterior temporal lobe (Noppeney et al., 2007). This form of damage produces inconsistent testing results, this is often interpreted as arising from intermittent access to semantic representations.

HSVE patients show significant category-specific effects, usually performing worse at living things than artifacts; while global aphasia patients, with mainly left hemisphere parietal lobe damage, have been found to have the opposite impairment; forming a double dissociation (Shallice & Cooper, in-press). Very precise forms of semantic impairment have been documented:

category-specific deficits, in which patients cannot name objects within distinct categories; modality-specific deficits, in which only a certain kind of sensory input, e.g., vision, is impaired; and interactions of the two. Category-specificity supports a modelling-based explanation, as does SD.

Functional brain imaging, neurological, and neuropsychological evidence hint towards a distributed semantic system, with various areas of activation responsible for specific kinds of processing at different category levels (Tyler et al., 2003, 2004). Additionally, combined with the current modelling frameworks, of which an analysis follows, there is also support for the existence of biological neural networks that facilitate the formation of attractors for the representation of concepts.

1.2 PDP Models of Semantic Memory

There has been some success in the field of parallel distributed processing modelling of semantic memory, with some models reproducing effects very similar to those seen in patients under semantic testing. An overview of two frameworks that model distinct and overlapping parts of the functionality of the semantic system is given. Focus is directed, mainly, on the first, the Rogers et al. (2004) model, which shall be used as the main architectural and theoretical basis for the current model, albeit with some modifications. The latter, the Gotts and Plaut (2002) model, contains a neurobiologically derived model of neuromodulation, which, is proposed as an addendum to the former model. Both models suggest an equivalence between their various unit layers and cortical regions, and deficits seen in patients are explainable based on their architectures and their respective emergent properties: attractors, and neuromodulation.

1.2.1 The Rogers et al. Model

Rogers et al. (2004) propose that an amodal semantic store emerges from the relationships between modal perceptual representations such as vision and language. Thus, semantic knowledge is an abstraction of high-level information that emerges as a product of statistical learning mechanisms. Such behaviour is inherent to neural networks that, provided the required connectivity exists, have the ability to compute such cross-modal mappings, thus encoding the regularities found in their environment. According to Rogers et al. (2004) the cortical area, the anterior and inferolateral temporal cortex, being modelled as the central semantic hub is connected to high-level perceptual and motor areas which are held to contain distinct modal representations.

The model consists of a network of bidirectionally connected units depicted in figure 1. Units are divided into two layers: *visible*, and *hidden*; the visible units are further subdivided into three categories: *name* units, *verbal* descriptors, and *visual* features. The hidden units form what is called the *semantic* layer of the network and are the only units that, by definition, do not receive direct environmental input. These units form the amodal store.

The visible unit subdivisions reflect the different input streams available to the system. A unit in the verbal layer represents some linguistic aspect of a concept: a name (e.g., “mammal”, “bird”, “cup”); a visual percept (e.g., “has eyes”, “has wheels”); a functional property (e.g.,

Figure 1: A high-level architecture of the model (Rogers et al., 2004, fig. 1).

“can fly”, “can roll”); or an encyclopaedic fact (e.g., “lives in Africa”, “found in kitchen”). A unit in the visual layer describes high-level visual information, in much the same way. These two visible categories of units are postulated to each represent a distinct anatomical cortical region which has specialised in the detection of specific properties.

The visible units have the ability to function as both input and output. The system is able to accept any of the aforementioned visible unit subsets as input, producing as output the remaining visible units¹. The semantic layer is hypothesised to be Wernicke’s proposed transcortical association area, similarly specialising in detection of properties over and above the other two layers (Eggert & Wernicke, 1977).

Based on an analysis of semantic attributes of animals and artifacts carried out by Garrard et al. (2001), Rogers et al. (2004) created a set of prototypes; see figure 2. The training stage is likened to a child’s learning process of the semantic meaning of words, although the inputs and outputs of the model are not equivalent to those of the whole cognitive system; because the model deals with high-level data, preprocessed by other specialised brain areas.

The training set consists of patterns the correspond to living creatures and non-living objects: birds, mammals, fruits, vehicles, household objects, and tools. Each category is made up of concepts that share a large proportion of features. In the case of living creatures there are features: common to all animals, to birds and mammals; some found only in birds or only in mammals; and some idiosyncratic units found on only in exceptional cases, this allows for the encoding of semantic outliers (e.g., a bat). For the names of each pattern a mapping is used by which most patterns have a unique name (e.g., “robin”, “lorry”), while others share a general top-level category name (e.g., “bird”, “vehicle”). Names are represented by a single unit being on. This is to avoid the encoding of any specific structure within a name; in the same way “cat”

¹Polymodality, the ability to accept input/output via the same stream, i.e., completing a pattern given any sub-pattern, is important as it allows the network to model the same tasks carried out by the patients: naming pictures, providing a verbal description, defining names and drawing/copying pictures (Rogers et al., 2004).

does not contain the word “mammal”, although they both may refer to the same creature.

Once the network is trained the weights store semantic knowledge, i.e., the connection weights have encoded the mappings between the inputs and outputs, allowing the network to produce the correct pattern when given a part of it. Thus, semantic representations have emerged, in an abstract form, as a function of the architecture and the similarities encoded a priori in the input patterns².

In the trained model each input has its own attractor, which is the stable set of states of the semantic units when the given pattern is applied over the visible units³. The internal representations, the attractors and the weights that give rise to them, form the amodal semantic store which has derived a structure that is not reflected in a single modality (Rogers et al., 2004).

After training, the model undergoes a lesioning procedure. This involves disconnecting units, by zeroing the connection weights between them at random and in increasing quantities. The semantic tests given to impaired patients are emulated by the lesioned network, which produces a similar pattern of performance. This is given as evidence that the model manages, on some level, to capture the nature of the deficits and of semantic memory.

The behaviour of the lesioned model allows for conclusions to be drawn about how semantic memory may degrade in SD. In the model this behaviour is due to the collapse of attractors; presumably because their basins grow or get deformed due to the introduction of noise, resulting from degradation of normal connectivity. As lesioning increases the damage, the system is unable to differentiate similar attractors, which previously was possible due to access to every feature. Subsequently, neighbouring (categories of) concepts merge into one, more general, super-category.

From this modelling framework, it can be seen that the proposed area of the temporal cortex may exist with the functionality and properties described: an amodal, homogeneous, semantic store; the required connectivity and high-level inputs appear to be in place. Although, it cannot be the only seat of semantic processing, it plays an integral role. In addition, semantic errors, like mistakes in the specificity of naming a stimulus, can be explained by underlying damage to attractors.

1.2.2 The Gotts and Plaut Model

Gotts and Plaut (2002) base their modelling framework on the distinction between two different kinds of possible damage that could be incurred by the semantic system, based on Warrington & Cipolotti (1996). The first is *access/refractory* damage: attributed, in this model, to the malfunctioning of the neuromodulatory system, which is in charge of amplifying neural signals, aiding appropriate activation, and suppressing refractory-like effects. The second is the same form of damage seen in Rogers et al. (2004): the severing of connections to, from, and between the semantic units, resulting in a *degraded semantic store*.

²For more details see figure 4 in Rogers et al. (2004).

³The semantic structure of the attractor states is related to the similarity structure of the input patterns, see figure 5 in Rogers et al. 2004, for the clusters of patterns produced by their model.

In order to model access/refractory damage the system incorporates *synaptic depression* (Abbott et al., 1997), a form of neural refractoriness, and a simple neuromodulatory process that is consistent with the effects the neurotransmitters *norepinephrine* (noradrenalin) and *acetylcholine* have on the brain (Varela et al., 1999). Neurotransmitters modify the behaviour of groups of neurons, affecting how they respond to signals. The systems that produce acetylcholine and norepinephrine do so to facilitate bottom-up processing of modal input, by reducing the refractory effects caused by synaptic depression (Gotts & Plaut, 2002).

The model is composed of a feed-forward neural network with three layers: *phonological*, *hidden*, and *semantic*. The input to the system is via the phonological units, proposed to correspond to Wernicke’s area, the left inferior frontal and posterior temporal cortices. Phonological input is connected in a feed-forward way through a set of hidden units, to the semantic units, which are paralleled with the inferior temporal and parietal cortices, postulated to function as the brain’s semantic region (Gotts & Plaut, 2002).

Training data is based on a spoken word-picture matching test from Warrington & Cipolotti (1996); thus, the model is limited to just emulating auditory word comprehension. The network is trained, using backpropagation through time, on a set of input and target output patterns, which are applied respectively to the phonological and semantic units. The input-output pairs, phonological patterns coupled with semantic meanings, are assigned at random. The frequency at which each pattern pair is found in the environment is variable, so a percentage of concepts are more commonly encountered, resulting in a more stable knowledge of some concepts. Familiarity towards some patterns and not others is not modelled in Rogers et al. (2004), despite the strong familiarity effect SD patients show⁴.

The outputs, the semantic representations, reflect a hierarchy by design. This precludes the system from creating its own semantics, in contrast to Rogers et al. (2004). A related point is also that the feed-forward architecture does not allow for the emergence of attractors or for polymodality, again in contrast to Rogers et al.’s model. These characteristics subtract from the model’s explanatory power.

Purposefully impairing the system involves two forms of damage: randomly removing a proportion of the connections; and disrupting the neuromodulatory system, by altering unit firing properties. The latter is equivalent to reducing the concentration of neurotransmitters, thus crippling the system with synaptic depression. The lesioned system is given a semantic task, and appears able to consistently model both the access/refractory deficient and the degraded store groups, showing significant rate, semantic relatedness, serial position, consistency, and frequency effects.

As mentioned, each semantic representation is provided as input to the system, undermining the modelling framework. In addition, the network does not involve any feedback connections, considered by Gotts and Plaut (2002) as biologically implausible. Despite these drawbacks, the model provides a good fit to the patient data, based on the distinction between types of damage, and successfully models a simplified version of synaptic depression and neuromodulation.

⁴Although, there exist models such as the one described in Rogers & McClelland (2004) that capture these effects, within a framework similar to Rogers et al. (2004).

1.3 Aims of this Study

This project consists of a re-implementation of the Rogers et al. (2004) model, albeit with a different underlying implementation, namely a Boltzmann machine. The project aims to: *a)* create a training set; *b)* produce a neural network able to form internal representations; and *c)* emulate the test results of SD patients.

The model is expected to produce internalised representations with a semantic structure reflecting that of the hierarchically organised input patterns, showing a tight grouping of animals and a more sparse structure for artifacts. In addition, it is anticipated that it will provide a good fit to the patients' data in a qualitatively similar way to Rogers et al. (2004), and by appealing to the underlying nature of the BM, the test results can be accounted for.

Reimplementing the Rogers et al. (2004) model as a Boltzmann Machine is not just an academic exercise. If successful it will help to clarify which aspects of the Rogers et al. model are theoretically critical and which are mere implementation details.

2 A Boltzmann Machine Model of Semantic Memory

The current model is based on a modified version of Rogers et al. (2004), a high-level diagram of which can be seen in figure 1. The main divergence is that this implementation is realised using a kind of neural network called a Boltzmann machine (BM). The rationale behind this hinges on two factors: BMs offer some biological realism; and they have been shown to be appropriate for this kind of task (Hinton & Sejnowski, 1986), as they are a type of attractor neural network; see subsection 2.1.3.

In this section, the BM architecture is explained along with implementation-specific details. Subsequently, the set of training patterns and the internal representations of the model are described.

2.1 The Boltzmann Machine

A BM is a type of stochastic, constraint satisfaction neural network based on statistical thermodynamics (Ackley et al., 1985). It is an extension of the Hopfield neural network model that incorporates simulated annealing, and is composed of units connected using bidirectional symmetric links (Hinton & Sejnowski, 1986). Units have a binary state that is determined probabilistically based on its neighbours and the weights on the links to it; a connection weight can take any positive or negative real value.

The units are divided into visible, v , and hidden, h . Each visible unit is connected to all the hidden units, but not to any other visible unit; whilst hidden units are fully connected; giving a total of $(v + h - 1)(v + h)/2$ weights. Visible units function as the interface between the BM and its environment. Hidden units capture “underlying constraints in the ensemble of input vectors that cannot be represented by pairwise constraints among the visible units” (Ackley et al., 1985, p. 154) and are always free, unclamped. After training a non-empty subset of the visible units may be clamped, in which case the network’s weights will calculate the remaining free unit states, resulting in pattern completion (Hinton & Sejnowski, 1986).

2.1.1 Interpretation of Network States

The activity of a BM unit can be interpreted as acceptance of a domain hypothesis, if it is on, or rejection, if it is off. The weight of a link between two units represents a weak constraint on the two hypotheses; a positive weight means the two hypotheses support each other (i.e., if one unit fires, it is likely the other also will) and a negative weight indicates neither hypothesis should be accepted (Hinton et al., 1984).

When the visible units are clamped the BM seeks to locate a configuration of hypotheses that minimises the global energy. This energy, the extent to which the BM’s configuration violates the constraints imposed by the environment (Hinton et al., 1984), is defined as:

$$E = - \sum_{i < j} w_{ij} s_i s_j + \sum_i \theta_i s_i \quad (1)$$

where w_{ij} is the weight, or connection strength, between unit i and j , s_i is the state of unit i (on is 1 and off is 0), and θ_i , the threshold⁵, is a self-regulatory parameter applied to each unit (Ackley et al., 1985).

Finding the global minimum in the energy landscape is not guaranteed. At best what can be done is to perform a search for local energy minima, by switching every unit's state to the one which lowers most the total energy (Hinton & Sejnowski, 1986). Due to the network's nature this energy gap, between accepting the k th hypothesis and rejecting it, can be calculated locally, on per unit basis, using:

$$\Delta E_k = \sum_i w_{ki} s_i - \theta_k \quad (2)$$

where k is a unit that will fire if its input is above its threshold, θ_k (Ackley et al., 1985).

2.1.2 Simulated Annealing, Thermal Equilibrium & Learning

Local minima are by definition not optimal and thus, the BM must be able to avoid or escape from them. This is accomplished by allowing units to fire probabilistically; amounting to introducing noise into the network, permitting jumps between states of different energy (Hinton et al., 1984). The probability that a unit k will fire is set to:

$$p_k = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\Delta E_k/T}} \quad (3)$$

where ΔE_k is k 's energy gap (see equation 2), and T is the temperature (Ackley et al., 1985). As T approaches 0, thermal equilibrium, the relative probability of two global states⁶ follows the Boltzmann distribution. Due to the inherent properties of this distribution, in order to reach equilibrium a process called simulated annealing must be applied to the network⁷.

The equation used to update the value of each weight, the learning rule⁸ is:

$$\Delta w_{ij} = \epsilon(p_{ij} - p'_{ij}) \quad (4)$$

where ϵ , the learning rate, moderates the effect the difference between the two probabilities has on w_{ij} (Ackley et al., 1985), p_{ij} is the probability of units i and j both being on when all the visible units are clamped, the plus phase, and p'_{ij} is the probability of the units co-occurring when the BM is running freely at thermal equilibrium, the minus phase (Hinton et al., 1984).

The learning rule, as mentioned, uses only locally available information to optimise a global energy measure (Hinton et al., 1984). It has the ability to make the spontaneous behaviour of the network in the minus phase mimic that of the plus phase, by only observing how often units i and j are on at thermal equilibrium (Hinton & Sejnowski, 1986).

⁵Also known as a bias, b_i , if it is inverted: $b_i = -\theta_i$.

⁶A global state is a set of all unit states; there are 2^{v+h} possible global states.

⁷For a detailed account of the reasons behind this, see Hinton and Sejnowski (1986).

⁸For the mathematical derivation of the BM learning algorithm see the appendix in Hinton and Sejnowski (1986) or in Ackley et al. (1985).

2.1.3 Motivation for Using a Boltzmann Machine

Using a BM instead of the back-propagation architecture used by Rogers et al. (2004) allows for testing whether the form of damage proposed by Rogers et al. (2004) is successful dependent on their specific neural network architecture (Plaut & Shallice, 1993) or if it is a more universally applicable modelling strategy. Another important feature of BMs is they allow the emergence of attractor basins that are a fundamental property of this framework, forming the substrate for concept formation (Hinton & Sejnowski, 1986).

Additionally, BMs have biologically plausible components. Their learning rule is a function of only locally available information: each connection needs only to know the states of the two units it connects, in order to send signals. This is simple, indicating that it could, in theory, be performed by real neurons; as opposed to, e.g., backpropagation which is described as being neurologically implausible⁹ (Rumelhart et al., 1986). Additionally, weight strengths are only altered by small amounts (Hinton & Sejnowski, 1986); only one kind of signal, a simple numerical value, is sent through the network, making effective use of connections; the computing units are small (Ackley et al., 1985); and the connection and computation specifications are within the confines neurobiological plausibility (Hinton & Sejnowski, 1999).

The reason biologically plausible components are preferable, even though this is a model, is because it is possible to capture more than just the current level of analysis, allowing for behaviours to arise that were not necessarily predictable a priori. E.g., the low-level neuromodulatory system in Gotts and Plaut (2002) is inspired by neurobiological data and, due to this, manages to give rise to complex higher-level memory deficits.

Despite its simplicity, learning is very slow. This is a substantial detraction from its usefulness and realism, as the cognitive system often retains knowledge very quickly, seemingly without any training. Although, for the specific task of semantic memory modelling, this substantial lack of learning speed may be appropriate, as the semantic system does have a dissociable slow-learning component (Rogers & McClelland, 2004).

2.2 Implementation Specific Details

The programming language used to implement the BM, and the rest of the software for the model, is C. The C programming language allows for the fast execution of programming code, which is important for implementing learning in BMs as it is very slow. Although, a relatively low-level language, it allows for flexibility. To complement the C code-base a graphical user interface was written using GTK+, a (widget toolkit) library for C. These design choices are educationally valuable as they ensure understanding of the algorithms, in addition to appropriately implementing the BM.

The model-specific BM settings required to faithfully implement Rogers et al. (2004), include restricting the number of visible and hidden units, and creating the set of training patterns. The units comprising the network are the visible, $v = 215$, and the hidden units, $h = 64$. The input

⁹Backpropagation through time is used in Gotts and Plaut (2002), and presumably used in Rogers et al. (2004), since it is used in Lambon Ralph et al. (2007), which is derived from it.

units are divided into 40 name, 64 visual, 111 verbal units, of which: 61 are perceptual, 32 are functional, and 18 are encyclopedic. It should be noted that, although these values are based on Rogers et al. (2004), figure 1 is misleading, as perceptual and encyclopedic units should be equal to those in figure 2.

There are $v \times h$ connections between the visible and hidden units and $h \times (h - 1)/2$ between the hidden units. Given the values of v and h , 87% of connections carry information into and out of the semantic layer, and 13% are intrinsic to it. As in the Rogers et al. (2004) model there are no visible-to-visible connections. This is congruent with the connectivity of classic BMs.

Initialisation of the BM consists of setting each connection weight to a uniformly distributed random value in the range: $[-0.2, 0.2]$, and randomly setting the unit states to either on, 1, or off, 0. The annealing process (see subsection 2.1.2) starts at temperature $T = 100$, with a thermal energy decay rate of 0.9, cooling down to 0.001. The network is sampled 100 times for collecting co-occurrence statistics of units (see equation 4). For the value of ϵ and updating the weights, see subsection A.7.

Units in the model are abstractly implemented, without a specifically allocated memory storage. They are represented by the integer indices of the various arrays which hold their related values, e.g., the index 0 corresponds to the first visible verbal name unit, and so its state is accessed via the 0th element in the array of states.

The connections between units are similarly not implemented, except in the form of mapping functions. This involves taking the indices of the two units, i and j , that are connected¹⁰; providing output as a single integer in order to index the bidirectional connection weight array.

To find the connection weight between, e.g., index 0, the first of the visible, and 215, the first of the hidden units, a visible-to-hidden mapping function is used, which computes $vj + i$. In this case, the two units are mapped onto the 46225th element of the weights array. To find a hidden-to-hidden unit connection weight a similar function is used: $vh + (j - 1) + i(2h - i - 3)$. This method uses less computational time and space, as opposed to a two-dimensional array, which would have allocated double the amount of connection weights for the hidden-to-hidden pairs of units and would have needed to compensate for the bidirectionality of the links by checking for redundancy.

2.3 Patterns

There are three input streams available: names, verbal descriptors, and visual attributes. The second source provides features apparent in a number of visually presented items, collected by asking participants to write down a list of properties. The third provides a set of visual attributes collected by analysing participants' drawings of the same stimuli. These two sources of features were used by Rogers et al. to create a set of pattern prototypes.

All three forms of input are high-level forms of information that are assumed by Rogers et al. (2004) to be the output of other cognitive processing, containing sets of discrete features. No

¹⁰Only visual and hidden or two hidden unit indices are acceptable, this is a constraint imposed by both the BM and the model by Rogers et al. (2004).

light is shed by Rogers et al. (2004) on how these feature sets are computed. The model’s scope is limited, in this sense, to just capturing the potential interactions between these features, and not the lower-level, presumably equally semantic, process by which they were extracted.

2.3.1 Verbal Input

Garrard et al. (2001) asked participants to list properties they thought were important to describe a set of stimuli. A cherry was found to have, amongst others, the following features: “has pip”, “is red”, “can be picked”, and “is found in trees”.

The verbal descriptors are the most detailed subpatterns (the longest feature vectors) and so are, by definition, the most helpful form of information to provide and, conversely, the most difficult output to compute for the model. A verbal description of an item was standardised to contain: 61 perceptual, 32 functional, and 18 encyclopedic properties; as reflected by the structure of the verbal units, although this distinction has no functional repercussions for the model.

2.3.2 Visual Input

Visual features were collected by analysing drawings of the concepts, produced by participants by matching the visually discernible features of those drawings, with those given in Garrard et al. (2001). Thus, creating a set of visual features per pattern¹¹.

2.3.3 Name Input

The natural language name of a stimulus is assumed to be arbitrarily related to its corresponding verbal and visual representations. E.g., the word “robin” does not provide any information about the bird in question. Neither does a phonological relationship exist between “robin” and “bird”, despite them potentially pertaining to the same animal and, by extension, concept. For this reason, Rogers et al. (2004) decided to encode each name as containing one uniquely active unit. Architecturally, this one-to-one correspondence means each name unit represents a specific name, so 40 names in the training set require 40 name units. Intuitively, as reflected in the model, names are the least information-rich source of input, and thus are the most difficult to learn.

In Rogers et al. (2004), most patterns are assigned unique base-level names (e.g., “car”), although some are instead linked with a more general name (e.g., “vehicle”). Based on this, two approaches of training were explored in the BM model. The first is directly derived from Rogers et al. (2004), allowing for the explicit naming of categories. The second is a simplified version of the first, in which patterns have no category- or domain-level names. The former could be used for testing as, due to the problems discussed in subsection 2.4, its pre-lesioned version does not perform near enough to healthy patients. Thus, the latter was used in the semantic testing

¹¹For a detailed analysis of the raw data of the features of concepts from Garrard et al. (2001) and their drawings see figure 2 in Rogers et al. (2004).

Figure 2: Prototype feature vectors used to generate visual (top) and verbal (bottom) representation patterns for the model. Plus signs indicate units likely to be active for items in the category (turned on with $p = .8$), zeros indicate idiosyncratic units that are less likely to be active for items in the category ($p = .2$), and dashes indicate units that are never active for items in the category. hh = household. (Rogers et al., 2004, fig. 3)

phase: for each category (mammals, birds, tools, vehicles, household objects¹²), 8 patterns were generated, resulting in a training set of 40.

2.3.4 Pattern Similarity Structure

Patterns were generated using figure 2, a probabilistic set of prototypes. The training sets based on it have a qualitatively similar inherent structure. In this specific set of patterns, living creatures share around 13.5% of their features, i.e., they are present in both mammals and birds (mammals share 8.8%, birds share 5.6%); inanimate objects only share approximately 3.3% of their features (tools share 8.8%, vehicles share 7.4%, household objects share 5.6%). The imbalanced structure between domains is apparent.

In order to fully uncover the structure present in the training set, a hierarchical cluster analysis was performed. This allows for: *a*) evaluation of the prototype itself, as a means of creating the required categories; *b*) prediction of the possible semantic categories that may emerge as a product of training the model; and *c*) locating potential outliers (e.g., a bat, categorised as a mammal but with the ability to fly like a bird).

Following Rogers et al. (2004), similarity was calculated as the ratio of total number of attributes not present in either of the two items over the of the total number of unique attributes

¹²The category of fruit, which appears to fall between living and inanimate objects, is not used in testing in Rogers et al. (2004). This is because they failed to collect the equivalent patient data.

Figure 3: Dendrograms showing the clusters in the verbal (left) and visual (right) input, including fruit; equivalent to figure 4 Rogers et al. (2004).

Figure 4: A dendrogram showing the clusters for each whole pattern, including fruit.

listed across the pair of items¹³. This measure of dissimilarity, Jaccard distance, J_δ , is computed using:

$$J_\delta(p, q) = \frac{|p \cup q| - |p \cap q|}{|p \cup q|} \quad (5)$$

where p and q are two patterns, sets of binary features.

Jaccard distance is an intuitive notion of dissimilarity. The rationale behind using J_δ as a measure (in contrast to, e.g., Euclidean distance) is that the present, but not the absent, features in each pattern are of importance (Kaufman & Rousseeuw, 2005). Absent features cannot, in this specific model, increase the similarity found between patterns (e.g., both a pig and a car do not have wings, this fact should not affect their similarity); this property arises because each feature is an asymmetric binary variable. As J_δ is only concerned with features that co-occur, it does not take into account joint absences (Aldenderfer & Blashfield, 1984). This view of the bit patterns reflects the way the BM models its environment.

The hierarchical clusters created by analysing the verbal and visual streams, are shown in figure 3; the two dendrograms show the J_δ between each pattern. The horizontal lines represent sets of similar patterns, decreasing in cardinality, leading to, on the far right, singleton sets, labelled appropriately. The closer to the right bifurcations, indicated by vertical lines, occur the more similar the patterns within clusters are. E.g., animals have a lower dissimilarity than

¹³The definition given in (Rogers et al., 2004) is of the Jaccard similarity coefficient and not of the Jaccard distance, calculated by subtracting the coefficient from one.

artifacts, from this it can be concluded: non-living things share fewer verbal attributes than do animals. The labels used in the dendrograms correspond to each (sub)pattern. They are related to underlying bit patterns only in the sense that the categories match: a pattern called a “mouse” is a mammal; they are provided to facilitate reading.

From an overview of the dendrograms¹⁴ it is seen that in both the verbal and visual input streams non-living objects are distinguishable from animals. Mammals and birds, share features, but also form two separable subgroups. The inanimate objects are divided into fruit and vehicles, in the case of verbal input, and a more arbitrary mix of household objects, vehicles, and tools. Household objects, are a context-sensitive classification; a wide range of objects can be found in a house. Fruits form a subcategory within the inanimate objects in the verbal, although in the visual input they are evenly dispersed within the inanimate objects¹⁵.

Using the whole pattern (combining the name, verbal, and visual parts) to create a dendrogram, see figure 4, provides an amodal view of the similarities between items in the training set. This dendrogram shows the subcategories found previously are more finely discernible into their own specific clusters. So it is expected that if the model is provided with every feature of a pattern, it will be able to closely mirror these classifications. Thus, an ideally trained system is predicted to have a structure of semantic representations that reflects the one described here.

2.4 Training in the Model

The network was trained for 31,000 epochs which took approximately one month of processing time; for details on the training algorithms see appendix A. Error initially decreased rapidly and stagnated at 1.8% per unit (see figure 5)¹⁶. The final result, at 31,000 iterations, means that for about 1.75% of the time a visible unit is in the opposite state to what it should be¹⁷. This statistic is an overall approximation for all three combinations of input/output, and as such is an overestimation, e.g., the error for a verbal input, to a name and visual output, asymptotically approaches 0.0%. At the pre-lesioned phase of each semantic task, see section 3, it performs at healthy levels.

Due to time constraints, imposed both by the project and the nature of the BM (1,000 iterations take approximately 24 hours), this error level could not be reduced. Proposed possible causes for the lack of convergence are: *a*) the biases were not initially set to high negative values, Rogers et al. (2004) assigned them to an untrainable value of -2 ; *b*) the number of hidden units is too low and thus cannot capture the fine details of the environment; *c*) the weights are too

¹⁴The two dendrograms in figure 3 are equivalent to those in figure 4 by Rogers et al. (2004), although their dendrograms do not show the structure of the tools category.

¹⁵This is in opposition to the training set generated by Rogers et al., who performed post-processing on the fruit patterns to make them even more distinct from the household objects and tools; no indication of why this was done, nor why they did not update the prototypes to accommodate this, is given. Although, this has no implication on the test results since fruits are not used in the evaluation of their network’s performance.

¹⁶This error is time consuming to calculate, hence it is computed once per 1,000 iterations.

¹⁷Using a different set of training patterns, with general names included, the identical behaviour was also encountered. This set (see figures 3 and 4) is the one the internal representations in figure 6 are created from. The weights arising from this training set could not be used for testing, as it could not perform well enough, e.g, at confrontation naming it makes around 33% omissions, 2.8% superordinate, and 2.8% co-ordinate errors.

Figure 5: The error graph during learning.

large, despite increments/decrements being small, and thus do not facilitate energy jumps (this can be fixed by adding a weight decay coefficient); and/or d) co-occurrences are not collected enough times and thus a bad approximation to the BM’s state space is used to update the weights.

During training the model learns to name animals before it can name inanimate objects: at around the 6,500th training cycle it correctly names approximately 14/16 animals, but can only name 10/34 artifacts; the mistakes are omissions, presumably not activated above the needed threshold. The model learns animals first because there are fewer of them, and they presumably form a more compact attractor, as expected.

2.5 Internal Representations

Once trained the states of the hidden units correspond to the BM’s semantic state. Euclidean distance is used to measure the differences between internal representations; each unit found on does not correspond to a feature being present. On the contrary, the semantic unit states represent the statistical correlations extracted from the input patterns, functioning as high-level feature detectors.

The internal categorical structure is shown in figure 6; the model has an understanding of the difference between mammals and birds, and living and non-living objects. The high-level structure of the relationships between the model’s attractors reflects that of the inputs. Capitalised words indicate the representation that is activated for a generic instantiation of that category. The categories given such a general name are directly copied from Rogers et al. (2004). These labels can be seen as archetypal members of their respective categories, e.g., “MAMMAL” denotes a standard member of the respective category, meaning that “pig” appears to be the

Figure 6: A dendrogram showing the clusters created internally by the BM to model the input patterns, this version includes fruit and category-level names, seen in capitals.

most generic mammal.

3 Evaluating the Model

As seen in section 2, the model is able to learn the structure of the modal input, creating a conceptual store comparable to a healthy semantic system. In this section, damage is imposed on the network, and the post-lesioned versions are subjected to a range of testing.

The tasks modelled here are based on those completed by subjects in Rogers et al. (2004) and Lambon Ralph et al. (2007). In these studies, patients with semantic dementia (SD, a degraded store deficit), herpes simplex encephalitis (HSVE, an access impairment), and healthy participants (as a control group) were asked to demonstrate their semantic abilities in: naming objects, matching stimuli with their corresponding words, and drawing, copying or delayed drawing of the items. These tasks serve the purpose of evaluating which semantic abilities are present in the various populations.

3.1 Modelling Damage

To parallel the impairments caused by SD and HSVE, Lambon Ralph et al. (2007)¹⁸ propose two forms of damage to model each type of cortical pathology. One consists of randomly removing a percentage of connections from, to, and within, the semantic layer, thus causing the permanent loss of conceptual information¹⁹. The other involves introducing a uniformly distributed amount of noise across all connection weights, proposed to impair access to such knowledge.

The main difference between lesioning and disrupting the links between units, is that the latter is expected to preserve connectivity, therefore activations continue to spread through the network, albeit in a biased way; whereas in the former case such information is permanently lost. The nature of the BM model means that, as seen in Rogers et al. (2004), following damage semantically similar concepts merge into one larger attractor. Thus, it is expected that in the tasks, a pattern consistent with such degradation will be revealed.

In order to implement lesioning connections, a proportion of the weights²⁰ are set to a value of 0. Zeroing is applied over a randomly selected subset of the weights for 20 different times per each severity of lesioning. This is to avoid particularly significant weights lesioned in one case, but not in another, affecting the overall score, e.g., the score for 40% of connections lesioned is a mean over 20 models.

Connection weights are found to have a mean of -0.83 and a standard deviation of 3.63 . In the case of noise, the span of values added to the weights starts from the least severe range of

¹⁸Lambon Ralph et al. (2007) is an extension of Rogers et al. (2004) to include damage proposed to cause an access-like pattern of impairment.

¹⁹Limiting connectivity has been found, in some cases more obviously than others, equivalent to removing the units themselves (Hinton & Shallice, 1991; Bullinaria & Chater, 1995), although damaging subsets of connections does not map well onto neurological evidence (Shallice & Cooper, in-press). The reasons behind removing connections blindly, in varying proportions, and without taking into consideration whether or not they are intrinsic to the semantic layer or projections from/to it, is not addressed by Rogers et al. (2004). Additionally, they do not take into account if some connections are more important than others or how this may affect their coarse-grained grouping of similarly lesioned models.

²⁰The weights that carry information into and out of the semantic layer make up 87% of the total connections; see subsection 2.2 for more details.

$[-0.5, 0.5]$ through to the most severe range of $[-5.0, 5.0]$ ²¹. Each severity level of this form of damage is averaged over 20 times, as with zeroing weights.

3.2 Confrontation Naming

The confrontation naming is a standard neuropsychological assessment measure for semantic memory. Within the task subjects are asked to name a line-drawing, and subsequently their responses were classified into the following categories: *a) correct*, the answer most often given by control subjects; *b) superordinate error*, the category of the name given matches that of the target but is more general (e.g. mammal, or animal, instead of mouse); *c) co-ordinate error*²², both the given and the target name are from the same semantic domain (e.g. cat instead of dog); and *d) error of omission* for all remaining responses, including none.

Patients with SD are highly anomic, a characteristic that increases with the progression of the disease. In contrast, HSVE patients show less severe naming difficulties, but nonetheless produce erroneous responses. For this reason, confrontation naming is modelled, a useful task for checking the degree of word-finding difficulties.

3.2.1 Modelling Method

The model emulates this test by clamping the appropriate subset of input units with a pattern's visual features. Subsequently, annealing takes place to reach a stable semantic state. Finally, the name units are measured to locate which unique unit is most often on. The model is thus equipped with a means of naming each visually presented subpattern. The threshold used to detect activation of naming units is taken from Rogers et al. (2004). If a naming unit is uniquely on for more than 50% of the times tested for the same visual stimulus, it is selected as the given response and classified into one of the error types, otherwise it is considered an omission.

3.2.2 Overall Naming Results

The graphs in figure 7 show the overall results of three SD patients, along with three severities of lesioning in the model, selected based on how closely they score to the patients²³. The relative ordering of proportions of error types is the same as that seen on the patient's scores; with omissions being the most frequent, then co-ordinate errors, and finally cross-domain errors near zero.

The proportion of omissions grows as that of correct responses decreases. This is due to increasingly less input reaching the semantic units and, the inverse phenomenon, a decreasing amount of semantic output reaching the naming units. Thus, disconnecting units causes the BM to produce activity that does not exceed the threshold value, resulting in an omission. Cross-domain errors are unaffected by the extent of damage. This is because the network has

²¹These ranges are analogous to those used in Lambon Ralph et al. (2007), taking into consideration the ratio between the noise added the weights and their respective statistics.

²²In Rogers et al. (2004) and Lambon Ralph et al. (2007) this is called a semantic error.

²³No HSVE patient scores were available for comparing noise damage in the BM model to their form of impairment.

Figure 7: Naming results for SD patients (left), from figure 6 of Rogers et al. (2004), and BM model (right), taken at 5%, 15%, and 35% of connections removed.

been trained to link the names of animals and artifacts to their visual features; zeroing weights cannot cause any cross-domain naming to occur, as such confusion would require a new visual-to-name units mapping. Co-ordinate errors are seen to reach approximately 0.1, and then drop back to zero. This is due to base-level attractors merging into a larger more uniform category-level basin of attraction, so the name output is from close semantic associates (neighbouring concepts within the same attractor). Co-ordinate errors return to a value of zero after a certain amount of damage because name units are not uniquely activated and/or responses are below the threshold.

On the left of figure 8 are the HSVE patients' naming scores that show an equal amount of errors per type, this is in contrast to the SD patients'. As seen previously in figure 7, SD causes substantially fewer co-ordinate errors and about double the amount of other errors than seen in HSVE patients. On the right is the model data for the two types of damage, with lesioning severity chosen to produce a matching proportion correct to that of the patients. Both forms of BM damage show a similar pattern, reproducing the SD patients' naming abilities. Therefore, the introduction of noise appears to create similar results to zeroing weights; at a noise range of $[-0.5, 0.5]$, no access-like pattern can be seen.

3.2.3 Naming Results in Different Domains

Rogers et al. (2004) propose that due to differences in the structure of the patterns that form each category, the accuracy of naming should vary dependant on the semantic category being tested. Scores in the domains of animals and artifacts are shown in figure 9 for both patients

Figure 8: Naming results for SD and HSVE patients (left), from figure 4 of Lambon Ralph et al. (2007), and for the BM model (right) at 10% connections removed and with a range of $[-0.5, 0.5]$ of noise added.

and the BM model. The model’s results appear to follow a similar pattern to those responses given by the SD patients for each proportion of error.

3.3 Word-to-Picture Matching

In Rogers et al. (2004) SD patients were presented with a word that they needed to relate to a line drawing. The pair of pictures contained the target and a close, dissimilar, distant, or unrelated foil. The two patients were asked to select one picture from each such pair, presented as a two-way forced choice decision.

3.3.1 Modelling Method

Initially the model is presented with a name, to correspond to the presentation of a written word; annealing takes place and the stable states of the hidden units are recorded. The name is then unclamped and a visual input is given. The possible visual patterns are: the *target* (e.g., swan); a *close* distractor, selected at random from the same category as the target (e.g., duck); a *distant* distractor, selected from an alternative category but within the same domain (e.g., dog); and an *unrelated* distractor, chosen from the opposing domain (e.g., chair). For each of the four visual subpatterns applied to the network the hidden unit states are saved. The internal states corresponding to the target and to each visual foil are compared in a pairwise manner to that of the name. The semantic activity closest, measured in Euclidean distance, to the name is selected as the BM’s response, in accordance with Rogers et al. (2004).

Figure 9: SD patients' (left), tested by Rogers et al. (2004), and model's (right) results in animal and artifact domains.

3.3.2 Longitudinal and Cross-sectional Results

In figure 10, following Rogers et al. (2004), the longitudinal deterioration of semantic abilities is related to an increase in proportion of lesioning. An abrupt loss of word-to-picture matching abilities is seen between 20% to 30% percent of connections removed. While there is no patient data to compare this to, the BM replicates the performance in the Rogers et al. (2004) model.

In a cross-sectional analysis of matching words to their respective pictures, see figure 11, the BM model does not capture the errors seen in patients. Under the distant and unrelated conditions the model, at 40% of damage, performs at ceiling values for the both the distant and unrelated foils. Rogers et al. (2004) present cross-sectional data for their model at a lesioning of 20% of the total connections, as this scored closest to the two SD patients. In comparison to the BM model it appears their model is less robust to disconnecting units, in general.

Figure 10: The BM model's performance in word-to-picture matching of models in increasing severity of damage.

Figure 11: The responses for the BM model at 40% of connections lesioned (left) and for two SD patients' (right) from Rogers et al. (2004), figure 10.

4 Discussion

One of the main objectives of this project was to demonstrate that the theory underlying the Rogers et al. (2004) model could be implemented in a Boltzmann machine (BM) architecture this aim has been achieved. The BM is equipped with the ability to create an amodal semantic store with the same qualitative properties as that of the set of training patterns, taken from prototypes defined in Rogers et al. Thus, the model has a learned hierarchical semantic store, able to perform categorisation and semantic tasks in much the same way as healthy subjects.

In addition it has been shown that the form of damage, i.e., removing connections, used by Rogers et al. (2004) for modelling SD, is applicable to the BM model. Thus, the conclusions drawn by Rogers et al. are independent of the back-propagation training algorithm. Additionally, the modelling framework has been explored and a more complete picture of what was carried out by Rogers et al. has been obtained.

4.1 Modelling Neural Damage

The model was evaluated by first damaging in a theoretically justified way and then comparing its performance to that of patients' on two semantic tasks. The first task consists of producing a name for each stimulus and the second task involves matching words to corresponding pictures. Following Lambon Ralph et al. (2007), two forms of damage were explored zeroing a subset of connections and adding noise to connection weights. The severity of damage was carefully selected to match the semantic dementia (SD) and the herpes simplex virus encephalitis (HSVE) groups of patients.

4.1.1 Semantic Dementia

The results obtained in the confrontation naming task show the BM model providing a match to both the SD patients and the Rogers et al. (2004) model in their responses for each error type; see subsection 3.2. However, the good data fit is a function of the threshold, which directly alters the relationships between the three forms of error: fewer or more responses are classified under co-ordinate and cross-domain errors, as opposed to omissions. This is problematic as no explanation is given in Rogers et al. (2004) for the selection of the threshold value. Additionally, no mention is made to the fact that the inclusion of the threshold, in some ways, acts as an executive process over the network, as it decides which activations are selected for output and which are ignored. A second issue in modelling the confrontation naming task is that naming can only occur at the lowest level in the BM model, since the model does not support naming at the superordinate level, i.e., category or domain names, e.g., “mammal” or “animal”²⁴.

That the BM model produces names for items at proportion correct levels comparable to SD patients, shows that attractor dynamics are able not only to function as distilled amodal semantic representations, but also to account for the various errors produced by the patients.

²⁴There is evidence that points towards higher-level naming taking place in a slightly different cortical area (Tyler et al., 2004), than the one being modelled in Rogers et al. (2004) (Shallice & Cooper, in-press).

This lends credibility to the existence of such attractors in the real semantic system, as damage to them produces patient-compatible data. Specific attractors, after disconnection of an increasing proportion of units, coalesce into more general attractors; the closer their basins were prior to damage the more likely it is they will merge to form more generalised semantic concepts. The damage caused by disconnecting units culminates in attractors losing their ability to categorise as finely as before. The animal domain is less affected by this form of damage since it collapses into a single larger basin of attraction, producing errors that are within the same category. Artifacts are disadvantaged in this respect, due to being sparsely scattered in the healthy semantic space, they cannot create a stable enough internal state resulting in a higher number of omissions. However, in general, both categories are qualitatively affected in the same way.

Unfortunately, the model could not be matched to the least severe SD patient of Rogers et al. (2004), who correctly named the items 80% of the times tested (see Rogers et al. figure 6). The current model, even with 2.5% of connections lesioned could not correctly name over 60% of the visually presented subpatterns. This indicates either that the BM model has a less robust set of internal representations (possibly due to insufficient training), or that the naming threshold was too stringent (or both). Additionally, a small discrepancy between the patients and the model can be seen in the proportion of co-ordinate errors at the first data point of figure 7, possibly for the same reasons.

Turning to the second test, the word-to-picture matching task a longitudinal graph was created showing the model's deteriorating abilities as a function of the proportion of connections removed (see figure 10). This is comparable to the results shown in figure 10 of Rogers et al. (2004); as there is no equivalent patient data, there is no way to determine if these longitudinal results are realistic. In a cross-sectional analysis at one level of degradation (see figure 11), that also includes the scores in tests with distant and unrelated distractors, the model is less able to capture the patient results, except in the close distractor condition. The lack of convergence to the patients' data may be due to insufficient sampling for the matching task. In Rogers et al. (2004) every single word-to-picture combination was sampled. In evaluating the current model, time constraints prevented such a long experiment. Alternatively, the lack of convergence may be due to the current model remaining more stably in the target attractor. It should also be noted that performance on this task is assessed by looking directly at semantic units. Rogers et al. (2004) do not explain how this is mappable onto patients. This semantic comparison of the distances between the various global states can be construed as crude executive processing, performing operations over and above the built-in semantic abilities.

4.1.2 Herpes Simplex Virus Encephalitis

The HSVE patient data in the confrontation naming task could not be matched by adding noise to connection weights, as proposed by Lambon Ralph et al. (2007). This form of damage involves applying a disturbance to every weight. In Lambon Ralph et al. (2007) it produces scores that match those of the HSVE patients tested. Nonetheless, this method lacks neurobiological

realism. It was conceived by Lambon Ralph et al. (2007) after the inner workings of their model were understood, as a means of obtaining the needed category-specific results. There is no clear neurological basis for the assumptions behind this form of damage since HSVE is found to involve a decrease in grey matter. Equally, there is no compelling evidence for its location (between visible and hidden or hidden and hidden units) or extent (the range of the uniform distribution for the noise).

In the BM model adding uniform noise to each connection weight caused a pattern of responses similar to that produced by disconnecting the weights. Thus, the results show that disrupting connections does not produce an access-like pattern of responses, as seen in HSVE. With noise the connections still forward activations, although they do so with a random disturbance. Neither, does this form of impairment model the other needed characteristics of access damage: repetition and frequency effects. In patients with HSVE these effects change over both time and amount of exposure to the same stimuli. A much more promising way to capture the access deficit is using the approach of Gotts and Plaut (2002), as described in appendix B²⁵.

4.2 Proposed Improvements and Extensions

The Rogers et al. (2004) model, despite being successful in many respects, as a first step towards explaining semantic memory and deficits thereof, appears to have some pitfalls. These are of varying importance.

Some criticisms of the model stem from its lack of an executive area, whose function is to select the appropriate internal representation (Jefferies et al., 2008). Executive control is useful in cases where it is presumed more than one concept is produced by the activations in the semantic store. It might also be in control of decisions being made at various category levels, so some form of an iterative procedure exists, using the available feedback to (re)classify stimuli, e.g., a “dolphin” might first lead to the “fish” attractor, and only on further consideration lead to “mammal”. Thus, the model “cannot be a complete account of semantic cognition because all information is activated in a rigid fashion” (Jefferies & Lambon Ralph, 2006, p. 2114), i.e., the lack of dynamic context-sensitive task-appropriate executive semantic control. Such an addition might prove to describe a larger proportion of semantic deficits, e.g., those of semantic aphasia patients, as proposed by Jefferies et al. (2010).

Another kind of critique is centred on the usefulness and appropriateness of taking for granted the high-level output produced by the various somatosensory sources. What is defined as input is not equivalent to the input that the cognitive system receives, i.e., direct environmental stimuli. It is, in fact, a statistically analysed set of feature vectors. This modal, motor, and linguistic “input” is actually the output of a very sophisticated process that could arguably be considered part of the semantic system and not external to it. The extraction of features from the environment is tantamount to semantic processing. Thus, for a model to be successful in obtaining semantic knowledge it should not rely on preprocessed input. This is a point

²⁵Adding uniform random noise over all the weights is a computationally straightforward addition to the model. In contrast, incorporating the Gotts and Plaut (2002) would require substantial modifications.

also highlighted by Borsboom & Visser (2008), in their review of a related model in Rogers & McClelland (2008). On the other hand, this may be setting very high expectations, as a system with direct access to raw real-word environmental stimuli would have to incorporate very sophisticated sensory pathways, seemingly leading to a model of the whole brain as opposed to just its semantic system.

The current modelling framework ideally intended to employ a combination of the methods used in both the Rogers et al. (2004) and the Gotts and Plaut (2002) models, by incorporating their strengths, and compensating for their weaknesses. As seen, there are various ways conceptual representations can be impaired. In order to explain impairments that are category- or modality-specific, or an interaction of the two, it might prove useful to look at what forms of damage may affect the semantic store both internally and its external links. This motivates the need for a hybrid approach, involving the general architecture of Rogers et al., especially the ability for semantic knowledge to emerge, combined with the neuromodulatory mechanisms discussed in Gotts and Plaut (2002).

4.3 Conclusion

The current model shows it is possible to use a BM to model some of the functionality of semantic memory. It is able to extract structure from its environment creating a hierarchical store of semantic knowledge. The BM uses such learned representations to classify visually and verbally presented stimuli. In accordance with impaired patients' data the model can emulate semantic tests post-lesioning. By appealing to the nature of its attractors which are compromised following damage, it can offer explanations as to how these deficiencies arise. Thus, fulfilling the expectations based on Rogers et al. (2004).

The model focuses on the regions affected by SD, without taking into account the fuller picture of a distributed semantic system. There are many directions in which the model can, and arguably must, expand, whilst being constrained by neuroanatomical and neuropsychological findings. Bearing in mind what it can account for, the model forms an invaluable starting point for further modelling frameworks.

References

- Abbott, L., Varela, J., Sen, K., & Nelson, S. (1997). Synaptic depression and cortical gain control. *Science*, 275(5297), 220–224.
- Ackley, D. H., Hinton, G. E., & Sejnowski, T. J. (1985). A Learning Algorithm for Boltzmann Machines. *Cognitive Science*, 9, 147–169.
- Aldenderfer, M. S. & Blashfield, R. K. (1984). *Cluster Analysis*. Quantitative Applications in the Social Sciences. Sage Publications.
- Borsboom, D. & Visser, I. (2008). Semantic cognition or data mining? *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 31(06), 714–715.
- Bullinaria, J. & Chater, N. (1995). Connectionist modelling: Implications for cognitive neuropsychology. *Language and Cognitive Processes*, 10(3), 227–264.
- Eggert, G. & Wernicke, C. (1977). *Wernicke’s works on aphasia: A sourcebook and review*. Mouton de Gruyter.
- Garrard, P., Lambon Ralph, M. A., Hodges, J., & Patterson, K. (2001). Prototypicality, distinctiveness, and intercorrelation: Analyses of the semantic attributes of living and nonliving concepts. *Cognitive Neuropsychology*, 18(2), 125–174.
- Gotts, S. J. & Plaut, D. C. (2002). The impact of synaptic depression following brain damage: A connectionist account of “access/refractory” and “degraded-store” semantic impairments. *Cognitive, Affective, & Behavioral Neuroscience*, 2(3), 187–213.
- Hinton, G. & Sejnowski, T. (1986). Learning and relearning in boltzmann machines. *MIT Press, Cambridge, Mass.*, 1, 282–317.
- Hinton, G. & Sejnowski, T. (1999). *Unsupervised learning: foundations of neural computation*. The MIT Press.
- Hinton, G., Sejnowski, T., & Ackley, D. (1984). Boltzmann machines: Constraint satisfaction networks that learn. *Cognitive Science*, 9, 147–169.
- Hinton, G. & Shallice, T. (1991). Lesioning an attractor network: Investigations of acquired dyslexia. *Psychological review*, 98(1), 74–95.
- Hodges, J. R., Patterson, K., Oxbury, S., & Funnell, E. (1992). Semantic dementia: Progressive fluent aphasia with temporal lobe atrophy. *Brain*, 115, 1783–1806.
- Jefferies, E. & Lambon Ralph, M. A. (2006). Semantic impairment in stroke aphasia versus semantic dementia: a case-series comparison. *Brain*, 129(8), 2132–2147.
- Jefferies, E., Patterson, K., & Ralph, M. (2008). Deficits of knowledge versus executive control in semantic cognition: Insights from cued naming. *Neuropsychologia*, 46(2), 649–658.
- Jefferies, E., Rogers, T., Hopper, S., & Lambon Ralph, M. (2010). “Pre-Semantic” cognition revisited: Critical differences between semantic aphasia and semantic dementia. *Neuropsychologia*, 48(1), 248–261.
- Kaufman, L. & Rousseeuw, P. (2005). *Finding groups in data: An introduction to cluster analysis*. Wiley.

- Lambon Ralph, M. A., Lowe, C., & Rogers, T. T. (2007). Neural basis of category-specific semantic deficits for living things: evidence from semantic dementia, HSVE and a neural network model. *Brain*, 130, 1127–1137.
- Noppeney, U., Patterson, K., Tyler, L., Moss, H., Stamatakis, E., Bright, P., Mummery, C., & Price, C. (2007). Temporal lobe lesions and semantic impairment: a comparison of herpes simplex virus encephalitis and semantic dementia. *Brain*, 130(4), 1138.
- Plaut, D. & Shallice, T. (1993). Deep dyslexia: A case study of connectionist neuropsychology. *Cognitive neuropsychology*, 10(5), 377–500.
- Rogers, T. & McClelland, J. (2004). *Semantic cognition: A parallel distributed processing approach*. The MIT Press.
- Rogers, T. & McClelland, J. (2008). Précis of semantic cognition: A parallel distributed processing approach. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 31(06), 689–714.
- Rogers, T. T., Garrard, P., McClelland, J. L., Lambon Ralph, M. A., Bozeat, S., Hodges, J. R., & Patterson, K. (2004). Structure and deterioration of semantic memory: A neuropsychological and computational investigation. *Psychological Review*, 111(1), 205–235.
- Rumelhart, D., Hinton, G., & Williams, R. (1986). Learning representations by back-propagating errors. *Nature*, 323, 533–536.
- Shallice, T. & Cooper, R. (in-press). *The Organisation of Mind*. Oxford University Press.
- Tulving, E. (1987). Multiple memory systems and consciousness. *Human neurobiology*, 6(2), 67–80.
- Tyler, L., Bright, P., Dick, E., Tavares, P., Pilgrim, L., Fletcher, P., Greer, M., & Moss, H. (2003). Do semantic categories activate distinct cortical regions? evidence for a distributed neural semantic system. *Cognitive Neuropsychology*, 20(3), 541–559.
- Tyler, L., Stamatakis, E., Bright, P., Acres, K., Abdallah, S., Rodd, J., & Moss, H. (2004). Processing objects at different levels of specificity. *Journal of cognitive neuroscience*, 16(3), 351–362.
- Varela, J., Song, S., Turrigiano, G., & Nelson, S. (1999). Differential depression at excitatory and inhibitory synapses in visual cortex. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 19(11), 4293–4304.
- Warrington, E. K. (1975). The selective impairment of semantic memory. *Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 27(4), 635–657.
- Warrington, E. K. & Cipolotti, L. (1996). Word comprehension: The distinction between refractory and storage impairments. *Brain*, 119, 611–625.

A Training Schedule

Training is the process of internalising the modal instantiations of concepts, in much the same way that a child builds the foundations of semantic meaning, by synthesising coherent concepts out of sensory and motor information. To follow, an overview is provided of the main training algorithms.

A.1 High-level Training

On every training epoch each one of the patterns is presented to the network. At each iteration the joint probabilities of the plus and minus phases need to be calculated, in order to adjust the unit weights, using algorithm 1, based on equation 4.

Algorithm 1 Training

```
while not trained do  
  plus phase  
  minus phase  
  adjust weights  
end while
```

A.2 Plus Phase

During the plus phase the network is run with the visible units clamped to a specific pattern, the hidden units are allowed to run freely (see algorithm 2). Before each (sub)pattern is clamped the global state is randomised, to remove any ordering effects.

In order to approximate the idealised distribution of states, the network is annealed for each specific pattern and analysed for co-occurrences²⁶. The joint probabilities over the whole network, in the plus phase and in the minus phases, to follow, are used to update the weights.

Algorithm 2 Plus phase

```
for  $pattern = 1$  to  $pattern_{max}$  do  
  randomise states  
  clamp( $p$ ) to visible units  
  anneal network  
  collect co-occurrence statistics  
end for
```

A.3 Minus Phases

Due to the 3 possible input-output pairs, there are 3 minus phases. In the first minus phase the name of each pattern is clamped, given as input, to the appropriate visible units thus making the output the verbal descriptors and visual features (see algorithm 3). Then the same pattern's verbal descriptor is clamped onto the BM's visible units with the remaining two, name and

²⁶This process is used to locate a stable enough set of states for the unclamped units (see subsection 2.1.2).

visual, in the role of output. In an equivalent way visual features are input, totalling three minus phases. So each of the three parts of a pattern take it in turn to be the input, in which case the remaining unclamped visible units serve as output.

After the input has been set, the network is annealed again, although, unlike the plus phase, the visible units are partially free, so the statistics which are collected now reflect what the BM has learned so far, per input stream.

Algorithm 3 Minus phase for names

```

for  $pattern = 1$  to  $pattern_{max}$  do
  randomise states
  clamp( $pattern$ ) to name units
  anneal network
  collect co-occurrence statistics
end for

```

A.4 Updating Unit States

Flipping states serially, as opposed to in parallel, is a limitation imposed on the model by the Von Neumann computer architecture, which executes instructions sequentially²⁷. As a compromise to this limitation, unit's states must be updated in a pseudo-random order; thus, approximating parallel events. Each unit i 's state, s_i , is set to *on* based on the probability, p_i ; see algorithm 4, which implements equation 3.

Algorithm 4 Updating unit states

```

for all  $i$  do
  calculate  $\Delta E_k$ 
   $p_i \leftarrow (1 + e^{-\Delta E_k/T})^{-1}$ 
  if random real  $\leq p_i$  then
     $s_i \leftarrow$  on
  else
     $s_i \leftarrow$  off
  end if
end for

```

A.5 Annealing

In order to reach an equilibrium in the BM's state space, simulated annealing is used, see subsection 2.1.2. This is done using algorithm 5; updating all unit states at decreasing temperatures, from a very high, t_{max} to a very low value, t_{min} , using a rate of thermal energy loss of t_{rate} . Annealing is also used when running the network, after training, to attain a stable response.

²⁷Ideally, if BMs could be implemented in parallel, on custom-built hardware, they would be dramatically faster.

Algorithm 5 Anneal network

```
 $t \leftarrow t_{max}$   
while  $t \leq t_{min}$  do  
  flip units( $t$ )  
   $t \leftarrow t \times t_{rate}$   
end while
```

A.6 Collecting Co-occurrence Statistics

When the network is at thermal equilibrium, co-occurrence statistics are collected for each visible-hidden (see algorithm 6) and hidden-hidden pair, for a number of times per pattern in order to closely estimate the distribution of states, based on equation 4. The value of p_{ij} , and equivalently that of p'_{ij} , are unnormalised in this calculation, thus each joint probability must be divided by $c_{max} \times pattern_{max}$, the product of the number of times the statistic is collected and the number of patterns in the training set. The unit states are updated once per co-occurrence count at a low temperature.

Algorithm 6 Collect visible to hidden co-occurrence statistics

```
for  $pattern = 1$  to  $pattern_{max}$  do  
  for  $c = 1$  to  $c_{max}$  do  
    update states  
    for  $i = 1$  to  $v$  do  
      for  $j = 1$  to  $h$  do  
        if  $on(s_i) \wedge on(s_j)$  then  
           $p_{ij} \leftarrow p_{ij} + 1$   
        end if  
      end for  
    end for  
  end for  
end for
```

A.7 Adjusting Weights

After both the plus and the minus phases for one value of i have been completed, the weight for each visible-hidden and hidden-hidden pair can be adjusted. This is done using a constant weight step, set to 0.01, as opposed to updating the weights using the difference between the two joint probabilities, $p_{ij} - p'_{ij}$, using equation 4. If $p_{ij} > p'_{ij}$, then w_{ij} is incremented by the step value, and inversely if $p_{ij} < p'_{ij}$, w_{ij} is decremented; the learning rate, ϵ , can be eliminated, see algorithm 7 (Ackley et al., 1985).

The advantage of this method is that it has been shown empirically to stabilise learning. It is an appropriate technique for some forms of energy landscapes, coping better than a proportional Δw_{ij} (Hinton et al., 1984).

Algorithm 7 Updating visible to hidden connection weights

```
for  $i = 1$  to  $v$  do
  for  $j = 1$  to  $h$  do
    if  $p_{ij} > p'_{ij}$  then
       $w_{ij} \leftarrow w_{ij} + \text{step}$ 
    else if  $p_{ij} < p'_{ij}$  then
       $w_{ij} \leftarrow w_{ij} - \text{step}$ 
    end if
  end for
end for
```

B Neuromodulatory System

The model proposed by Gotts and Plaut (2002), despite containing a sophisticated mathematical version of synaptic depression and neuromodulation, is a relatively simple feed-forward architecture. In contrast, BMs are bidirectionally connected and, the Gotts and Plaut model does not allow attractors, nor internal semantic representations, to arise, and it does not accept more than one form of input stream. The patients' data used by Gotts and Plaut is partitioned based on their apparent semantic deficiency: degraded store, or access/refractory damage; the latter of which is what motivates the inclusion of synaptic depression and neuromodulation.

Some of the neuromodulatory systems, consisting of chemical neurotransmitters, appear to be in charge of alleviating the effects of synaptic depression. These effects are applied on the individual synapse and neuron levels, but can nonetheless spread and cripple whole sub-networks of neurons in the neocortex. As shown by Gotts and Plaut (2002), this could produce stimulus-specific results.

B.1 Synaptic Depression

If a *pre-synaptic* neuron fires repeatedly, it causes the effect it has on a *post-synaptic* neuron to decrease. This effect, that of synaptic depression, is captured using a set of neurophysiologically derived equations created by Varela et al. (1999). The model consists of a variable scaling factor, which is a function of each unit's activity, imposed on all the connection weights.

Gotts and Plaut (2002) use spiking-based units with continuous values for their states, as opposed to the BM, which uses binary values; thus their equations are not directly applicable. They are presented below with proposed modifications both to them and to the BM's way of updating its states.

To calculate the total input received by a unit k , previously calculated using equation 2, the following is now used:

$$\eta_k = \sum_i w_{ki} s_i \rho(M) D_i - \theta_k \quad (6)$$

where w_{ki} , s_i , and θ_k are as previously defined, ρ is a scaling function applying the neuromodulatory effects of M on the pre-synaptic units (see equation 9), and D_i is the synaptic depression scaling factor (equation 8) (Gotts & Plaut, 2002).

The probability that a unit k will fire, previously equation 3, changes to:

$$p_k = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-g(\eta_k, M)/T}} \quad (7)$$

where g is a scaling function that accounts for post-synaptic effects of the neuromodulator M , and T is, as before, the thermal energy²⁸.

The synaptic depression factor for unit i , D_i , which has a fast and a slow component, $D_i = D_{i[f]}D_{i[s]}$, has also undergone modification²⁹, becoming:

$$\frac{dD_{i[c]}}{dt} = p_i\rho(M)(d_{[c]} - 1)D_{i[c]} + (1 - p_i\rho(M))\frac{(1 - D_{i[c]})}{\tau_{[c]}} \quad (8)$$

where c is the fast, f , or slow, s , component, and $d_{[c]}$ and $\tau_{[c]}$ are constants (Gotts & Plaut, 2002).

B.2 Neuromodulation

Acetylcholine and norepinephrine are proposed to be the central nervous system's mechanism of counteracting the refractory effects synaptic depression has on neural activity, by decreasing transmitter release in pre-synaptic neurons and increasing post-synaptic units sensitivity to excitatory input signals. Further supporting their inclusion in the model, memory impairments have been documented that are caused when the neuromodulatory system operates suboptimally (Gotts & Plaut, 2002).

These two chemicals have an important role: they effectively control the impact bottom-up, sensory and motor, input has on cortical processing, they “are likely to be involved in more global shifts of the information-processing state” (Gotts & Plaut, 2002, p. 194).

The pre- and post-synaptic effects are included in the Gotts and Plaut (2002) model and are presented here without modification³⁰. The pre-synaptic neuromodulatory effect is described by:

$$\rho(M) = \rho_{min} + \frac{(1 - \rho_{min})e^{-M}}{1 - e^{-M}} \quad (9)$$

where ρ_{min} is the minimum value of reduced transmitter release (Gotts & Plaut, 2002). At high values of M , as $\rho(M)$ approaches ρ_{min} , the effect pre-synaptic activity has on synaptic depression is greatly reduced, due to D_i being a function of $p_i\rho(M)$ (equation 8). At the same time, the pre-synaptic effect on η_k , the total input to the post-synaptic unit (equation 6), is also reduced, resulting in an overall decrease in sensitivity to input (Gotts & Plaut, 2002). On the other hand, when M takes large negative values, $\rho(M)$ approaches 1, synaptic depression increases.

²⁸Thermal energy is not part of the Gotts and Plaut (2002) model, but is nonetheless needed to continue to support annealing.

²⁹In BMs, p_{max} is 1.0, and therefore not included, although some form of constant scaling factor may be needed. For more details see appendix of Gotts and Plaut (2002).

³⁰Although the computation of g , since it is a function of η_k (see equation 6), is internally different.

The pre-synaptic effect of the neuromodulation process, used in the calculation of p_k , is:

$$g(\eta_k, M) = \eta_k(g_{min} + (g_{max} - g_{min})/(1 + e^{-M})) \quad (10)$$

where g_{min} is the minimum, and g_{max} the maximum, value by which the total input, η_k , can be scaled³¹ (Gotts & Plaut, 2002).

B.3 Effect on Model

One of the changes introduced by the aforementioned modifications is that now each unit must access its neighbours' probability of firing as opposed to merely their binary state, a property not present in the BM architecture, adding a new layer of complexity.

The probability of unit k firing, p_k , is presumably not affected by the incorporation of synaptic depression and neuromodulation, provided they are set at healthy levels. Damage to the neuromodulatory system is expected to amount to transient damage to active attractors, resulting in a stimulus- and therefore, category-, specific impairment.

B.4 Disrupting the Neuromodulatory System

Damage to the neuromodulatory system, in the Gotts & Plaut (2002) model, is shown to cause an access/refractory pattern, with large presentation rate and repetition effects combined with inconsistency in task scores. This is in opposition to patient's with SD, who are in the degraded-store category.

In the case of semantically related input, and therefore similar attractors, synaptic depression is expected to build up, causing the deficits seen in such patients. Once an attractor is affected by synaptic depression, within a malfunctioning neuromodulatory system, the network no longer can activate a representation corresponding to the current and any related input. Due to time limitations the model is not equipped to allow a modification of M . In theory such perturbations should produce results consistent with synaptic depression, making access to the affected attractors limited.

³¹If the input from unit i is lower than θ_k , g returns η_k , see equation 6.